

MULTISCALE COMPUTATIONAL HOMOGENISATION TO PREDICT THE LONG-TERM DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A fully coupled hygro-thermo-mechanical computational framework based on the multi-scale computational homogenisation is proposed for fibre reinforced polymers. At each macrostructure Gauss point, constitutive matrices for thermal, moisture transport and mechanical responses were calculated from the computational homogenisation of underlying representative volume element (RVE). A degradation model, developed from experimental data relating evolution of mechanical properties over time for a given exposure temperature and moisture concentration was also incorporated in the proposed computational framework. A unified approach is used to impose the RVE boundary conditions, which allows convenient switching between displacement, traction and periodic boundary conditions. A plain weave textile composite RVE consisting of matrix and yarns embedded in the matrix is considered in this case. Both matrix and yarns within the RVE were considered as isotropic materials. Furthermore, the computational framework utilises the flexibility of hierarchic basis functions and distributed memory parallel programming.

Key Words: *Multiscale computational homogenisation; Hygro-thermo-mechanical analysis; Fibre reinforced polymer; Textile composites*

1. Introduction

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites consist of mainly two constituents, i.e. glass, carbon or aramid fibres embedded in rigid polymer matrix. Due to their exceptional mechanical and chemical properties, FRP composites are commonly used in many engineering application including aerospace, ships, offshore platforms, automotive industry and civil structures [1]. Textile or woven composites is a class of FRP composites, in which interlaced fibres are used as reinforcement, which provides full flexibility of design and functionality due to the mature textile manufacturing industry [2]. On the other hand, during their service lives, FRP structures are exposed to harsh hygro-thermal environmental conditions in addition to mechanical loading, which leads to matrix plasticisation, hydrolysis and degradation of fibres/matrix interfaces [3]. These processes significantly reduce the mechanical properties of these structures. Therefore, fully coupled hygro-thermo-mechanical analysis based on multi-scale computational homogenisation strategy is vital for predicting the long-term durability of the FRPs structures, where microscopically heterogeneous representative volume element (RVE) is used to predict their macroscopic constitutive behaviour.

A plain weave textile composite RVE is considered here, consisting of matrix and yarns embedded in the matrix. These yarns are modeled with elliptical cross section and cubic spline paths. The multi-scale computational homogenisation framework is implemented in our group's FE software, MoFEM (Mesh Oriented Finite Element Method). A unified approach is used to impose the RVE boundary conditions, which allows convenient switching between displacement, traction and periodic boundary conditions [4]. Furthermore, the computational framework utilises the flexibility of hierarchic basis functions [5] and distributed memory parallel programming.

2. Model components

2.1. RVE boundary conditions

In computational homogenisation, an RVE is associated with each macroscopic Gauss point, the boundary conditions for which in case of thermal, moisture transport and mechanical problem are implemented using the generalised procedure proposed in [4]. The implementation of these boundary conditions are described here for the mechanical problem, which is straightforward to modify for the corresponding thermal and moisture transport cases. In matrix form these boundary conditions are given as

$$\mathbf{C}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{D}\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{g}, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = [\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx} \quad \bar{\varepsilon}_{yy} \quad \bar{\varepsilon}_{zz} \quad 2\bar{\varepsilon}_{xy} \quad 2\bar{\varepsilon}_{xz} \quad 2\bar{\varepsilon}_{zy}]^T$ is the macro-strain associated with a Gauss point. \mathbf{g} is the constraints applied to enforce the boundary conditions, while matrices \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} are given as

$$\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} d\Gamma, \quad \mathbf{D} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{H}\mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{X} d\Gamma. \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), \mathbf{N} is a matrix of shape functions, \mathbf{X} is a matrix of Gauss point coordinates and \mathbf{H} is a matrix specific to the type of boundary conditions used (e.g. displacement, periodic, traction).

2.2. Unsteady field problems

Conduction and diffusion models are considered for the heat transfer and moisture transport analysis, both of which are represented by the same governing equation

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} - K_{\psi} \nabla^2 \psi = 0, \quad (3)$$

where ∇^2 is Laplace operator, $\psi = T, c$ is scalar field (where T and c are temperature and moisture concentration respectively), t is time, ρ is density, C_p is specific heat capacity and K_{ψ} is thermal conductivity.

2.3. Degradation model

A fully generalised degradation model has been developed based on experimental data for the mechanical properties of FRP composites subjected to different hygro-thermal environmental conditions. The experimental data provided by our project partner at the University of Bath involves accelerated ageing, i.e. immersing of the FRP composites samples in hot distilled water with exposure temperatures of 25°C, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C, where different mechanical parameters (tensile strength, shear strength, young modulus and shear modulus) are recorded after 0, 28, 56 and 112 days. The proposed model can be used to predict the mechanical properties of the FRP composites with given histories of environmental exposure temperature and moisture concentration. The proposed model can be written in the rate form as

$$\frac{d}{dt} (1 - \omega) = -c\beta \ln \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_g} \right) (1 - \omega), \quad (4)$$

where ω is the isotropic damage parameter ($\omega = 0$ is equivalent to no degradation and $\omega = 1$ is fully degraded), T is the temperature, T_g the glass transition temperature, t is time and β is a material parameter and is estimated from the experimental data, c is moisture concentration ranges from 0 (dry) to 1 (fully saturated). The proposed degradation model is implemented using implicit Backward Euler Method.

2.4. Computational framework

The developed computational framework consists of series of micro and macro-level analysis, the detailed flow chart of which is shown in Figure 1(a). Both thermal and moisture transport problems are assumed as independent of each other and independent from mechanical problem. This assumption allow us to solve macro-level unsteady thermal and moisture transport problems independently, the conductivity matrices \mathbf{K}_T and \mathbf{K}_c for which are determined from the underlying RVEs. Both \mathbf{K}_T and \mathbf{K}_c are calculated only once and are used at each macro-level Gauss point. At each time step, temperature T and

moisture concentration c fields are saved to the macro-mesh, which are used subsequently in the calculation of degradation parameter $(1 - \omega)$. The damage parameter is approximated over the macro-mesh using

$$(1 - \omega)^h = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{q}_{(1-\omega)}, \quad (5)$$

where $(1 - \omega)^h$ is approximation of $(1 - \omega)$, \mathbf{N} is vector of shape functions and $\mathbf{q}_{(1-\omega)}$ is vector of nodal values of $(1 - \omega)$. At each time step, macro-mechanical problem consisting of linear elastic analysis is next solved using fully nested FE² algorithm, where at each macro-level Gauss point degradation parameter $(1 - \omega)$ is retrieved and pass onto the underlying RVE. Degradation of the form $\mathbf{D}_{matrix} = (1 - \omega)\mathbf{D}_{matrix}$ is considered only for the matrix part of the mechanical RVE, where \mathbf{D}_{matrix} is stiffness matrix of the matrix part. Homogenised matrix \mathbf{D} is calculated for each mechanical RVE and pass back to the macro-Gauss point to be used in the subsequent macro-level mechanical analysis.

Figure 1: Flow chart of the computational framework and representative volume element

3. Numerical example

For the macro-level structure, a three-dimensional block of dimensions $5m \times 5m \times 1m$ is considered, geometry and corresponding mesh for which are shown in Figure 2(a) and Figure 2(b) respectively. The RVE used in this case is shown in Figure 1(b). Both macro-structure and RVE are discretised with tetrahedral elements with 542 elements and 172 nodes in the case of macro-structure and 10285 elements and 2364 nodes in the case of the RVE. For the macro-level thermal problem temperature of $80^\circ C$ is applied to the top surface and constant heat flux is applied to the bottom surface. Similarly, for the case of moisture transport problem, a constant concentration ($1=100\%$ RH) is applied to the top surface and constant moisture flux is applied to the bottom surface. For the mechanical problem, the bottom surface of the block is fully fixed, while a constant traction of 1000 MPa is applied to the top surface. For the matrix material, thermal conductivity, density, specific heat, moisture diffusivity, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are 0.19 W/mm^oC, 1.2 g/cm³, 805 J/kg ^oC, 2.8×10^{-6} mm²/s, 3.5GPa and 0.35 respectively are used, while the corresponding values used for the fibres materials with the same units are 1.03, 2.53, 1000, 1.46×10^{-7} , 230, 0.26. Both thermal and moisture transport problems are solved with time step of 10 days for total of 110 days. At the end of the simulation, temperature and moisture concentration fields are shown in Figures 2(c) and 2(d) respectively. Heat conduction is faster as compared to moisture transport due to its higher value of heat conductivity. Furthermore, at the same stage, distribution of field $(1 - \omega)$ and vertical displacement u_y are shown in Figure 2(e) and Figure 2(f) respectively. As expected, area near the top surface of the block degraded relatively faster due to the higher concentration of temperature and moisture concentration. u_y relative to the first time step for the four points A, B, C and D shown in

Figure 2(b), are shown in Figure 2(g), which shows increase in u_y for a constant top surface traction with degradation of the block stiffness.

Figure 2: Numerical example geometry, mesh and results

4. Conclusions

A fully coupled hygro-thermo-mechanical computational framework based on multi-scale computational homogenisation is described for FRP composites. The proposed computational framework, which consists of a series of micro and macro analysis, is implemented in our group's FE code MoFEM. A parameterised geometry of the RVE is modelled with CUBIT using a python script, which gives us a flexible and automatic way to create an input file for MoFEM. A degradation model is developed from scratch from experimental data for the mechanical properties of the FRP composites. Finally, a numerical example is presented to demonstrate the correct implementation and performance of the proposed computational framework.

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